

Deliverable D1.3

Project ID	654241
Project Title	A comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure for analysing medical metabolic phenotype data
Project Acronym	PhenoMeNal
Start Date of the Project	1st September 2015
Duration of the Project	36 Months
Work Package Number	1
Work Package Title	Management
Deliverable Title	D1.3 Minutes of Kick-Off Meeting
Delivery Date	M2
Work package leader	EMBL-EBI
Contributing Partners	EMBL-EBI
Authors	Christoph Steinbeck, Namrata Kale, Kenneth Haug, Pablo Moreno
Abstract: This deliverable presents the discussions and decisions made during the kick-off meeting of the PhenoMeNal project.	
Version	Revised
History of changes: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Detailed objectives of the meeting 2. Details on action points concluded and task allocation 	

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1. Executive Summary

The PhenoMeNal project aims to address the challenges arising from the extreme data volumes in metabolomic phenotyping by creating a federated and high performance e-infrastructure that will support data processing and analysis pipelines from the earliest point of data acquisition to the generation of scientific knowledge. In order to meet this challenge, we have gathered a consortium of 13 European Partners with extensive experience in metabolomics research, tools development and provision of services as part of infrastructures and e-infrastructures. This highly collaborative and international nature of the project calls for an effective management infrastructure which would ensure efficient planning and monitoring of project activities, seamless communication across partners, robust and transparent decision making, balance in multiple responsibilities and competing priorities of consortium partners, prompt reporting and finally, successful delivery.

As a strategic initiative, a project kick off meeting was organised to develop a common understanding of the project objectives, task distribution, critical risks involved and the successful delivery of the project goals. The PhenoMeNal kick off meeting was organised at European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), Hinxton, Cambridge, UK by EMBL-EBI, the coordinator of the consortium, from 8-10 September 2015. Around 40 participants representing 8 European countries attended the kick off meeting. A detailed list of the participants is enclosed in the Annex 2.

This deliverable aims to report the main activities carried out in the frame of this work package deliverable, the presentations made for each Work Package (WP), interactions among different WPs in relation to the execution of deliverables and the overall legal, ethical, financial and administrative arrangements of the consortium.

2. Contribution towards work package objectives

- Efficiently manage the consortium activities to maximise PhenoMeNal impact
- Organise all PhenoMeNal consortium and stakeholder meetings, as well as regular staff exchanges between the PhenoMeNal partners in collaboration with our consortium partners
- Systematically document the decision-making process and decisions made in teleconferences, meetings and by mail exchange. This will be compiled regularly into PhenoMeNal consortium documentation.

3. Detailed Report on Deliverable

3.1. Objectives of the kick-off meeting

- Recap the information in the grant agreement, including the purpose of the project, the scope, deliverables and milestones, critical risks, estimated effort and budget, and the deadlines.
- Discuss the roles and responsibilities of the different partners and the synergies between them.
- Discuss the project management procedures with respect to the project plan and Management tools.
- Discuss the project management structure in terms of appointment of an autonomous advisory body e.g. the scientific advisory board (SAB).
- Critical risks assessment in terms of privacy and ethics during sensitive data handling and storage.
- Strategic planning for successful delivery.

3.2. Organisation and structure of the meeting and activities

The meeting was structured as a 3-days event.

- Day 1 was a plenary session with an overview of the whole project structure, the consortium agreement and legal implications, introduction of different partners of the consortium and special sessions on European Grid Initiative (EGI), EUDAT-European Collaborative Data Infrastructure and ELIXIR.
- Day 2 was focussed on presentations of the WPs and deliverables including the performance metrics followed by workshops and discussions on tools and workflows that will form the basis of the PhenoMeNal infrastructure. A comprehensive session on project management and outreach for the project was also accomplished.
- Day 3 included presentations on use-cases from practitioners within the consortia and what steps could be taken in context of workflows and data protection. The meeting was concluded with recommendations of experts for constitution of the PhenoMeNal Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and detailed planning for staffs exchange programs and workshops as foreseen for year 1.

A more detailed agenda of the meeting is reported in **Annex 1**.

3.3. Project objectives and management structure

The meeting was kicked off by an opening presentation by Chris Steinbeck (Project coordinator, EMBL-EBI). To set the tone for a successful launch for the project, the presentation included some key points on the vision for PhenoMeNal, project objectives and their implementation in form of networking activities, services and joint research activities, strategy for sensitive data management and protection, key challenges and critical risks in terms of data sharing and adoption by the wider community. In the frame of developing PhenoMeNal as an effective large scale e-infrastructure for high-throughput biomedical data management, the importance for the consortium to work in an ecosystem with relevant e-infrastructures such as Elixir (<https://www.elixir-europe.org>), EGI (<http://www.egi.eu>), EUDAT (<https://www.eudat.eu>) and, OpenMinted (<http://openminted.eu>) was discussed. The session also included a brief description of the overall management structure at the steering, management and operational level.

3.4. Partner presentations and their contribution to the overall project

The project introductory session was followed by a series of presentations from the consortium members. In this session, the Principal investigators (PIs) of the participating organizations EMBL-EBI, Imperial College of Science and Technology (ICL), Leibniz-Institute of Plant Biochemistry (IPB), University of Barcelona (UB), University of Birmingham (UoB), Consorzio Interuniversitario Risonanze magnetiche di metallo Proteine (CIRMMP), University of Leiden (UL), The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of Oxford (UOXF), Swiss institute of Bioinformatics (SIB), Uppsala University (UU), Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives (CEA) and Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (INRA), presented their expertise and role in the PhenoMeNal project in terms of skills, the computational and experimental facilities available (e.g. tools, high-performance computational abilities etc.) within their respective organisations. A brief overview about their previous participation in relevant projects and infrastructures was also presented.

3.5. Interfacing with relevant infrastructures

The plenary session also included some lightning talks from project leaders and representatives from relevant infrastructures such as EGI, EUDAT and Elixir. This initiative was taken to obtain indications useful to optimise possible synergies between the projects. Some of the major key points presented by the plenary speakers from the respective infrastructures were:

- The overall structure and goals of the individual infrastructures.

- Technical architecture in terms of services offered e.g. cloud computing, Virtual Research Community (VRC) portals.
- Data sharing, privacy and protection.
- Support and training initiatives including possible support that can be offered to PhenoMeNal.

The action items for the whole consortium that were concluded were:

- Possible use of the existing ELIXIR cloud activities.
- Working alongside EGI solutions for federated cloud services.

3.6. Project Structure and work packages

The second day of the workshop started with a plenary session for the individual Work Packages (WP) and their deliverables. In this session, the WP leaders (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9) presented the WPs under their flagships.

3.6.1. Work Packages

WP1 – Management

The tasks management and coordination of the consortium was presented by EMBL-EBI. A key point that was discussed during the presentation was about the financial risks in case of financial loss or bankruptcy of a partner.

WP2 - Sustainability of PhenoMeNal

The sustainability of PhenoMeNal beyond its initial 3-year funding period was presented by the WP lead from UL. The objectives of the WP in terms of interfacing with the relevant e-infrastructures, use of open source and sustainable tools, integration with companies, SMEs and publishers to support the development of global and sustainable approaches in the field were identified as important steps to achieve long term sustainability.

WP3 – Outreach and dissemination

The objectives, tasks, deliverables and the performance metric for dissemination and outreach was presented and discussed by WP lead University of Birmingham. The action points concluded were:

- Set early publication targets and participation in Metabolomics conference 2016 (<http://metabolomics2016.org>) for dissemination and outreach

Task allocation – All

WP4 - Interfacing with Biomedical and Electronic European Infrastructures

The general goal of the WP is to ensure that the major infrastructures in biomedicine in Europe have a preferential channel of interaction with PhenoMenal. The major lines of action in this respect were to:

- Interact with major e-infrastructures.
- Identify existing connections to other infrastructures through survey.
- Gather requirements from other relevant e-infrastructures.

Task allocation – *CIRMMP to lead*

WP5 - Operation and Maintenance of PhenoMeNal grid / e-Infrastructure

Grid/Cloud e-Infrastructure and VRC portal were the key features of the presentation by the WP5 lead from Uppsala University. Tasks under WP5 were discussed with respect to the provisioning of services, reference site for analysis on private data and a continuous integration system. The action points concluded were:

- Interaction with ELIXIR and EGI.
- Interaction between related WPs via regular hangouts.

Task allocation – *All*

WP6 - PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community Gateway

The PhenoMeNal VRC is described as the central access point for all users. It would provide an authoritative search for all containers, containers, Virtual Machine Images (VMIs), analysis tools, processes and pipelines, computing resources and datasets.

The discussions that followed resulted in the following action points:

- Need for an early User Experience workshop for the PhenoMeNal portal.

Task allocation – *EMBL-EBI*

WP7 – Privacy and Ethics

The discussion was led by the WP7 lead from ICL highlighting the importance of privacy and ethics when handling sensitive human data. The roles and responsibilities of the overall consortium to meet the ELSI requirements and the strategic plan of action to meet the targets were the important features of this session. The action points concluded were:

- Identify suitable experts for the SAB, stakeholder and data managers.

Task allocation – *All*

WP8 - Data Provenance, Compliance and Integrity

The WP is led by Oxford e-Research Centre who described the importance of the WP, the objectives, development of standards and working towards Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) principles. A communication plan was also discussed which underlined the use of:

- Need for regular staff-exchanges and hackathons for knowledge management.
- Google hangouts.
- Central Git/continuous integration/issue tracking.
- Shared working documents (Google docs).

Task allocation – *All*

WP9 - Tools, Workflows, Audit and Data Management

The WP focuses on the development and maintenance of the primary scientific and technological tools and corresponding interfaces. Led by IPB, the presentation discussed the dependencies between the different WP: Maintain and scale the tools required in WP5, produce reproducible, auditable and quality controlled workflows and to improve interoperability by adding WP8 data standards. Various tasks under the WP, the corresponding deliverables, audit requirements and data management were explicitly discussed.

3.7. Joint Research Activities

The PhenoMeNal consortium comprises expert research groups with outstanding achievements in Metabolomics infrastructure and methods development. While most of these tools are well established as stand-alone tools, a significant amount of research is needed to investigate the use and interoperability of these tools in a practically useful processing pipeline. The second session on day 2 was dedicated to talks and exhaustive discussions on such tools and workflows (e.g. W4M, <http://workflow4metabolomics.org>), the provision of running these tools by users on PhenoMeNal grid/cloud and the necessary software development, deployment and the test environment required.

The significant topics discussed and the resulting action points that were concluded were:

- Use of different cloud providers e.g. amazon cloud (AWS).
- Workflows and used cases for PhenoMeNal.

- Use of platforms like Galaxy (<https://galaxyproject.org>) for PhenoMeNal workflows.
- Licensing issues for different metabolomics tools.
- Integration of existing software into the VRC.
- Use of Jenkins (<https://jenkins.io>) for continuous integration for WP5.
- Policy document for code migration from closed source to open environments.
- Organisation of a PhenoMeNal GitHub repository for all the source code management.

Since the project aims to bridge the needs and solutions from a number of different disciplines including medicine, molecular biology and large scale IT infrastructure, data privacy and ethics were identified as critical issues that needed attention of the consortium. Clearly, respecting patient rights and protecting the privacy of patients and research subjects was considered an important objective for the project. Possible datasets as use cases Data protection acts, data anonymisation and Ethical, Legal and Social Implications (ELSI) in research were the key points that were discussed. The action points concluded were:

- Host an ELSI workshop involving experts in the field in order to understand the data privacy and issues.
- Acquire appropriate consent for datasets as use cases for PhenoMeNal.
- Probability of data provider form that would need to be completed by the data providers which would in turn ensure that all the ethical aspects of making data available, data sharing and use have been addressed.

Task allocation – *ICL*

3.8. Management tools and reviewed plan of work

The 3rd day of the meeting was used to discuss more on the effective management of the consortium including the planning for the meetings, workshops, staff exchanges and recommendations for the SAB for PhenoMeNal. The key discussion and action points concluded from the session:

- Pivotal tracker (www.pivotaltracker.com) was suggested tool for project management.
- Tasks were assigned in the pivotal tracker tool to the WP leads and participating partners.
- Responsible person for the deliverable will be the point of contact for reminders
- Importance of time sheets to record activities on a daily basis for all individuals participating in the project.

- The official consortium website as: phenomenal-h2020.eu
- A list of possible advisors for SAB was drafted and it was proposed that the relevant partners would invite the experts to set up the board. A copy of the extended synopsis of the project was decided to be circulated for project preview.
- Regular meetings and hangouts to discuss the progress of the project.
- Set up a developers' community or group that would meet early to decide on policies and guidelines.
- Plan was drafted for the possible workshops/staff-exchanges in year 1:

Table 1: Plan for workshops/staff exchanges in year 1

	Meeting/Workshop And total cost	When		Partner	Where	Comments
1	Annual stakeholder meetings	Y1	June 2016	EMBL-EBI	Dublin	Metabolomics Meeting
2	Privacy workshop	M3	Nov. 2016	ICL	ICL	Invite experts
3	Staff exchanges & Hackathons	Y1	October / November 2015	EMBL-EBI	EMBL-EBI	Software standards, procedures & Testing
		Y1	February / March 2016	UU	UU	Hands-on continuous integration, containerization, API design
		Y1	Q1 2016	EMBL-EBI + INRA	EBI	Integration of Metabolights/ MetExplore

						visualization
		Y1	Q1 2016	CEA with CNRS + INRA + EBI	TBC	Galaxy: Workflow management and tool integration
		Y1	Q4 Y1	EBI	EBI	Constructing pipelines with available tools
		Y1	Q3/Q4	OXF, IPB, EBI	OXF	Data standards
4	Clinical workshop	Y1	May/June 2016	UB+UU	Barcelona	

3.9. Use cases for PhenoMeNal

The final day of the meeting also included discussion on some of the used case aspects for the project. These included presentations from metabolomics experts within the consortium (ICL, CIRMMP, UL and UU). The talks were focussed on workflows for the project, role of metabolomics in preventive and precision medicine and the role of PhenoMeNal in addressing the challenges in metabolomics. The talk on “NPC workflow and PhenoMeNal pipelines” by ICL introduced the facilities and the role of the National Phenome centre in facilitating integration of metabolic profiling technologies into epidemiological and clinical research as well as serving as an international data collection hub. The talk described the different spectroscopic techniques (e.g. NMR, LC-MS) and the datasets produced and the workflow in terms of data generation, data acquisition, pre-processing and quality control. The current shortcomings of the process and the possible solutions offered by PhenoMeNal in terms of:

- Scalability.
- Interoperability in terms of acceptable community standards.
- Traceability: auditing and reporting of analysis to an agreed standard.
- Future-proofing which includes the extension of utility of existing datasets .

- Robustness in form of a systematised and validated statistical analysis.

The session also included talks from PhenoMeNal partners presented the metabolomics facilities in their respective organisation, various metabolomics platforms, workflows and their IT requirements, challenges for managing such a data workflow under a quality system, cost effectiveness and the corresponding solutions offered by PhenoMeNal.

4. Conclusions

The project kick-off meeting was an initial and successful management effort to revisit the goals and objectives of the project and was seen as a good opportunity to assign roles and responsibilities, general approach and timelines of the project, management and to voice specific issues and concerns including exploring the possible opportunities to interface with the relevant e-infrastructures.

5. Annexes

Annex 1
PhenoMeNal Kick-Off Meeting Agenda
Draft agenda

Time	Description
Day 1: 8th September 2015	
12:30 - 13:30	Arrival and Lunch (<i>Conference Centre</i>)
13:30 - 14:00	Introduction (Chris) Tour de Table (All)
14:00 - 15:30	Partner presentations. Max 3 slides and 5 minute each!!! <ul style="list-style-type: none">● EMBL-EBI● ICL● IPB● UB● UL● CIRMMP● UoB● UOXF● SIB● UU● CEA● INRA
15:15 - 15:45	Coffee & Tea
15:45 - 17:45	EGI & EUDAT & Elixir presentations (20 min each) + 1h discussions
End of day 1	
18:30 - late	Dinner at the Conference Centre for all

Day 2: 9th September 2015

- 09:00 - 10:30 Work package deliverables and organisation.
- **10 mins max**
 - Presentation of Deliverables and Milestones, **not Q&A session**
 - Hiring status
- Coffee & Tea available outside the room
- Plan for engaging with other partners committed and otherwise involved in the WP
- WP1 - Management. **EMBL-EBI**
 - WP2 - Sustainability of PhenoMeNal. **UL**
 - WP3 - Outreach and Dissemination. **UoB**
 - WP4 - Interfacing with Biomedical and Electronic European Infrastructures. **CIRMMP**
 - WP5 - Operation and Maintenance of PhenoMeNal grid / e-Infrastructure. **UU**
 - WP6 - PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community. **EMBL-EBI**
 - WP7 - Privacy and Ethics. **ICL**
 - WP8 - Data Provenance, Compliance and Integrity. **UOXF**
 - WP9 - Tools, Workflows, Audit and Data Management. **IPB**
- 10:35 - 11:15 **Tools and Workflows Development Workshop & Discussions (ALL)**
Kicked off by IPB Lightning talk and lead by IPB
=> What Building Blocks of the workflow will we have, what Platforms are we trying to focus on
- 11:15 - 12:00 **Cloud / Grid Workshop & Discussions (ALL)**

	Kicked off by UU Lightning talk and lead by UU <i>Alignment with other domains</i>
12:15 - 13:30	Photo outside Hinxton Hall Lunch (<i>Campus Canteen</i>) + Campus walk if weather & time permits
13:30 - 14:15	<u>Software development, deployment and test environments Workshop & Discussions (ALL)</u> Kicked off by Lightning talk and lead by EMBL-EBI
14:15 - 15:00	<u>Privacy & Ethics Workshop & Discussions (ALL)</u> Kicked off by Lightning talk and lead by ICL <i>Note: The Scientific and Technological Advisory Board will appoint one member to act as the PhenoMeNal Ethics Advisor.</i>
15:00 - 15:30	Coffee & Tea
15:30 - 16:30	Project Management and Outreach <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Project Plan Overview (<i>and early deliverables, M1-M12</i>)● Timesheets, <i>project will be audited!</i><ul style="list-style-type: none">○ All time recorded against WP (<u>and Deliverable?</u>)● WP meeting and reporting schedule examples:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ David, WP8○ Ola, WP5○ Steffen, WP9● Consortium Website<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ phenomenal-h2020.eu, phenomenal.bio, phenomenal.clinic○ The portal to the infrastructure (VRC)
	End of day 2
18:00	Bus to Cambridge
19:00 - late	<u>Dinner at Queens College Cambridge, in the “Old Hall”</u>

- Drinks from 19:00, sit down at 19:30

Day 3: 10th September 2015

- 09:00 - 10:00 **Short talks** by practitioners
- Jake Pearce (ICL)
 - Claudio Luchinat (CIRMMP)
 - Thomas Hankemeier (UL)
 - Kim Kultima (UU)
- 10:00 - 12:30 **Detailed planning of Year 1 (Goal: Y1 planned and agreed)**
- [Plan for future meetings](#)
- (10:30
refreshments) **Breakout sessions if required where WPs decide on short
term staff exchanges**
- Other:
- Use cases (clinical, lab-based) for what we hope to achieve
 - “Favorite” tools used today
 - Gathering requirements from Consortium Members as well as External Stakeholder (UX, Personas)
 - Assembly of the Scientific Advisory Board
- 12:30 - 13:30 Lunch (*Campus Canteen*)

End of meeting

Annex 2 List of Participants

No.	Name	Affiliation	Attendance		
			8 th Sept	9 th Sept	10 th Sept
1	Sven Bergmann	University of Lausanne	✓	✓	✓
2	Roger Mallol	University of Lausanne	✓	✓	✓
3	Rico Rueedi	University of Lausanne	✓	✓	✓
4	Marta Cascante	Universitat de Barcelona	X	✓	✓
5	Silvia Marin	Universitat de Barcelona	✓	✓	X
6	Vitaly Selivanov	Universitat de Barcelona	✓	✓	✓
7	Pedro de Atauri	Universitat de Barcelona	✓	✓	✓
8	Tim Ebbels	Imperial College London	✓	✓	✓
9	Robert Glen	Imperial College London	✓	✓	✓
10	Ibrahim Karaman	Imperial College London	✓	✓	X
11	Merlijn van Rijswijk	Netherlands Metabolomics Centre	✓	✓	✓
12	Thomas Hankemeier	Leiden University/NMC	✓	✓	✓
13	Michael van Vliet	Leiden University	✓	✓	✓
14	Steffen Neumann	IPB Halle	✓	✓	RP
15	Daniel Schober	IPB Halle	✓	✓	✓

16	Pierrick Roger Mele	CEA	✓	✓	✓
17	Etienne Thevenot	CEA	✓	✓	✓
18	Maxime Chazalviel	INRA	✓	✓	✓
19	Fabien Jourdan	INRA	✓	✓	✓
20	Florence Vinson	INRA	✓	✓	✓
21	Benjamin Merlet	INRA	✓	✓	✓
22	Ulrich Guenther	University of Birmingham	✓	✓	X
23	Karen Atkins	University of Birmingham	X	✓	✓
24	Claudio Luchinat	University of Florence and CIRMMP	✓	✓	✓
25	Antonio Rosato	CIRMMP	✓	✓	✓
26	Ola Spjuth	Uppsala University	✓	✓	✓
27	Payam Emami Khoonsari	Uppsala University	✓	✓	✓
28	Kim Kultima	Uppsala University	✓	✓	✓
29	Marco Capuccini	Uppsala University	✓	✓	✓
30	David Johnson	University of Oxford	✓	✓	✓
31	Susanna-Assunta Sansone	University of Oxford		RP	
32	Philippe Rocca-Serra	University of Oxford		RP	
33	Enol Fernández	EGI	✓	✓	X
34	Christoph Steinbeck	EMBL-EBI	✓	✓	✓
35	Namrata Kale	EMBL-EBI	✓	✓	✓
36	Kenneth Haug	EMBL-EBI	✓	✓	✓
37	Reza Salek	EMBL-EBI	✓	✓	✓
38	Kalai Jayaseelan	EMBL-EBI	✓	✓	✓
39	Pablo Moreno	EMBL-EBI	X	✓	X

40	Steven Newhouse	EMBL-EBI	✓	✗	✓
41	Gianni Dalla Torre	EMBL-EBI	✓	✓	✓
42	Dario Vianello	EMBL-EBI	✓	✓	✓

RP-Remote Participation

Annex 3 Photos

Photo 1. Photograph of the Consortium